

Bardet-Biedl Syndrome (BBS)- Exploring current perspectives with an update on overlapping condition and challenges ahead on multidisciplinary management

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ABSTARCT

Background: Diagnostic challenges in Bardet-Biedl Syndrome (BBS) with many of overlapping conditions corresponding to the patient's treatment management .

Case report: A 27-year-old male presented to the outpatient department with complaints of generalized fatigue for six months, accompanied by decreased appetite over the last 30 days. He reported no significant family history of similar conditions or consanguinity. The patient exhibited delayed intellectual milestones and was noted to have mental retardation. There was a history of delayed development of secondary sexual characteristics. Additionally, he had bilateral retinitis pigmentosa diagnosed in adolescence. On examination, the patient had Shortstature(+), Pallor(+), Post-axial polydactyly(+), Syndactyly(+), Gynecomastia(+), Micropenis(+) and Obesity(+). Vital signs were within normal limits. The patient was diagnosed with Bardet-Biedl Syndrome presenting with vitamin B12 deficiency anemia.

Conclusion: This case highlights the diagnostic challenge of BBS, particularly when presenting with overlapping clinical conditions. Comprehensive clinical evaluation and multidisciplinary management are pivotal in improving outcomes for such patients. Regular follow-up is essential to monitor and manage associated complications effectively.

Keywords: Bardet-Biedl Syndrome (BBS), vitamin B12 deficiency anemia, bilateral retinitis pigmentosa.

Introduction

Bardet-Biedl Syndrome (BBS) is a rare autosomal recessive disorder characterized by a wide spectrum of clinical manifestations, including retinal dystrophy, obesity, polydactyly, renal dysfunction, and hypogonadism, among others¹. It is a ciliopathy, resulting from defects in the primary cilia that affect various organ systems. The syndrome's phenotypic heterogeneity often delays diagnosis, and patients frequently present with overlapping clinical conditions².

The genetic basis of BBS is attributed to mutations in at least 18 identified genes, collectively referred to as BBS genes. These genes encode BBS proteins, integral to the function and structure of primary cilia—specialized cellular organelles involved in sensory perception, developmental signaling, and maintaining homeostasis. Mutations in these genes lead to ciliary dysfunction, which underpins the multisystem manifestations of BBS. Approximately 80% of cases involve mutations in the BBS1, BBS2, BBS10, and other BBS genes, emphasizing the complexity and heterogeneity of this condition^{3,4}.

Clinical manifestations of BBS include night blindness due to retinal dystrophy, postaxial polydactyly, hypogonadism, decreased IQ, and renal dysplasia. Associated conditions include diabetes mellitus, hypertension, congenital heart disease, facial dimorphism, speech problems, dental deformities, and liver failure. Despite the comprehensive understanding of BBS features, little is known about the association between BBS and megaloblastic anemia⁵.

Although Bardet-Biedl Syndrome primarily presents with these hallmark features, the overlap with other clinical conditions can obscure the diagnosis. Megaloblastic anemia due to vitamin B12 deficiency, as seen in this case, is an uncommon presentation of BBS⁶. The relationship between BBS and vitamin B12 deficiency remains poorly understood, with limited literature on this association. Anemia in BBS may result from nutritional deficiencies secondary to obesity, gastrointestinal anomalies, or metabolic disturbances, but its presentation necessitates thorough evaluation to rule out other contributing factors⁷. Here, we report a case of Bardet-Biedl Syndrome (BBS) in a young male who initially presented with generalized fatigue and was found to have megaloblastic anemia due to vitamin B12 deficiency.

Case Report

A 27-year-old male presented to the outpatient department with complaints of generalized fatigue for six months, accompanied by decreased appetite over the last 30 days. He reported no significant family history of similar conditions or consanguinity. The patient exhibited delayed intellectual milestones and was noted to have mental retardation. There was a history of delayed development of secondary sexual characteristics. Additionally, he had bilateral retinitis pigmentosa diagnosed in adolescence. On examination, the patient had Short stature (+), Pallor(+), Post-axial polydactyly(+), Syndactyly(+), Gynecomastia(+), Micropenis(+) and Obesity(+). Vital signs were within normal limits. Systemic examination findings included: Cardiovascular system: S1 and S2 heard without murmurs, Respiratory system: Normal vesicular breath sounds, Abdomen: Soft, non-tender, and Central nervous system: Glasgow Coma Scale score of 15/15. Initial laboratory Investigations revealed megaloblastic anemia with reduced serum vitamin B12 levels. Further evaluation included: Ophthalmological examination: Which confirmed bilateral retinitis pigmentosa, Hormonal studies: Which indicated hypogonadism and Genetic analysis: Which confirmed the diagnosis of Bardet-Biedl Syndrome. The patient was diagnosed with Bardet-Biedl Syndrome presenting with vitamin B12 deficiency anemia.

Management

The patient received oral vitamin B12 supplements and intramuscular vitamin B12 injections. Supportive treatment, including dietary modifications and other symptomatic care, was initiated. His symptoms of fatigue and appetite improved significantly during the hospital stay. The patient was discharged on Day 10 with advice for regular follow-up. The patient's general condition remained stable at follow-up visits, with marked improvement in anemia-related symptoms.

Table 1: The Diagnostic criteria of Bardet-Biedl Syndrome⁸

Primary Features	Present case
Rod-cone dystrophy	-
Polydactyly	+
Obesity	+
Learning Disabilities	+
Genital Anomalies	+
Renal Anomalies	-
Secondary Features	
Speech disorder/Delay	+
Strabismus/Cataracts/Astigmatism	-
Syndactyly	+
Development delay	+
Ataxia/Poor coordination/ Imbalance	-
Spinal Problem	-
Mild Spasticity	-
Diabetes Mellitus	-
Dental crowding/Hypodontia/ Small roots/High arched palate	-
Left Ventricular hypertrophy/Congenital Heart Disease	-
Hepatic fibrosis	-
Anosmia	-

Figure 1: Upper limb and Lower limb post-axial polydactyly

Figure 2 : Retinitis pigmentosa

Discussion

Bardet-Biedl Syndrome is a rare, multisystem disorder often underdiagnosed due to its phenotypic variability. The primary clinical features—obesity, retinal dystrophy, polydactyly, hypogonadism, renal anomalies, and intellectual disability—manifest to varying degrees in different patients. In this case, the patient's presentation with generalized fatigue led to the initial diagnosis of vitamin B12 deficiency anemia, which masked the underlying systemic disorder^{9,10}.

Retinitis pigmentosa, a hallmark of BBS, is often diagnosed in adolescence or early adulthood and can significantly affect quality of life. The presence of hypogonadism, micropenis, and gynecomastia further pointed towards an endocrine dysfunction associated with BBS. Short stature and syndactyly are additional common findings in this syndrome¹¹.

BBS management is multidisciplinary, focusing on symptomatic relief and prevention of complications. Early identification and treatment of secondary conditions such as vitamin deficiencies, hormonal imbalances, and renal dysfunction are crucial⁹. This case underscores the importance of considering syndromic associations in patients presenting with seemingly isolated clinical features like anemia, particularly in the presence of intellectual disability and other systemic signs.

In the present study, the patient had four primary features including polydactyly, Obesity, Learning Disabilities, and Genital anomalies that fulfill the diagnostic criteria of Bardet-Biedl syndrome. Hassan S et al¹² case study reported that the patient had 4 primary features like Rod-cone dystrophy, Polydactyly, Obesity, and Learning disabilities. Similarly, Ahmed Elawad OM et al¹³ case study revealed that the patient was diagnosed with Bardet-Biedl Syndrome as fulfilled four items of the primary features (obesity, retinitis pigmentosa, post-axial polydactyly, and renal abnormalities).

Conclusion

This case highlights the diagnostic challenge of Bardet-Biedl Syndrome, particularly when presenting with overlapping clinical conditions such as vitamin B12 deficiency anemia. Comprehensive clinical evaluation and multidisciplinary management are pivotal in improving outcomes for such patients. Regular follow-up is essential to monitor and manage associated complications effectively.

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